

The Kinetics of the Decarboxylation of Malonanilic Acid in Resorcinol and Catechol

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Kinetic data are reported for the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol. The activation parameters are calculated, and compared with those previously reported for the decarboxylation of malonic acid. The results indicate that the decarboxylation proceeds through a transition complex mechanism.

CLARK¹ studied the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid in several non-aqueous solvents including aniline and quinoline and reported that the mechanism of the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid is different from that of malonic acid in polar solvents. Since the solvents resorcinol and catechol have never been the subject of kinetic study for the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid, the kinetics of this acid in these solvents were studied in order to ascertain whether it follows the same mechanism as that followed by oxalic acid², malonic acid³ and β -resorcylic acid⁴. The results strongly suggest that the mechanism for the decomposition of malonanilic acid in resorcinol and catechol is similar to that for oxanilic acid⁵, benzoic acid⁶ and oxamic acid⁷.

Experimental

Reagents :

The malonanilic acid used in this research was prepared by A. Agarwal and N. Rao, City Queens College, by heating equivalent amounts of malonic acid and aniline. The gift sample was recrystallized several times from distilled water and dried in an electric oven at 103° for 2 to 3 hr, then stored over magnesium perchlorate in a desiccator. It melted at 130.3°. White crystalline solids of resorcinol and catechol BDH, analar grade, were used as solvents without further purification. The colour of the molten solvents were found to be dark red.

Procedure

The progress of the reaction was studied by measuring the volume of CO₂ evolved. The apparatus and technique are similar to those described in previous articles⁶⁻⁸. About 50 g resorcinol and 50 g catechol were separately taken in each experimental run and 0.322 g sample of malonanilic acid, weighed in a small sample tube was placed on the movable probe inside the reaction vessel. The set up was then placed in the constant temperature oil-bath $\pm 0.05^\circ$ and when

thermal equilibrium was established, the reaction was started by dropping the acid in the solvent. The CO₂ was collected at room temperature in a measuring burette filled with water which had been previously saturated with carbon dioxide. The volume of CO₂ collected on complete decomposition was 40 ml. The decarboxylation of malonanilic acid was studied at four temperatures, in both the solvents, 99.77% of the theoretical yield being obtained in all the experimental runs. The plot of $\log(V_\infty - V_t)$ vs. t , was linear in all the experiments indicating that the reaction is of first order where V_∞ is the volume of CO₂ after complete decomposition and V_t is the volume at time t . The average rate constants were calculated from the slopes of the logarithmic plots and are tabulated in Table 1. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated using the absolute reaction rate equation based upon the data in Table 1 and are tabulated in Table 2, along with the data of malonic acid in the same

TABLE 1. RATE OF DECOMPOSITION OF MALONANILIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL

Run temp. °C	No. of data pairs	Av. $k_1 \times 10^4$ (sec ⁻¹)	No. of data pairs	Av. $k_1 \times 10^4$ (sec ⁻¹)
120	4	3.81	4	3.72
130	3	11.48	4	10.47
140	3	37.15	3	30.90
150	4	102.30	2	87.10

TABLE 2. ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONANILIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL

	Resorcinol	Catechol
E_a KCal.mole ⁻¹	37.02	35.26
$\log A$ (sec ⁻¹)	17.21	16.16
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ KCal.mole ⁻¹	36.21	35.50
$\Delta F^\ddagger$ KCal.mole ⁻¹	29.21	29.31
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal.deg ⁻¹ .mole ⁻¹	+19.1	+14.41

TABLE 3. ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONIC ACID AND MALONANILIC ACID IN SEVERAL SOLVENTS

	Malonic acid		Malonanilic acid	
	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal mole ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal.deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal mole ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal.deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
<i>m</i> -Cresol ¹	32.3	+ 3.2	33.2	+ 9.4
<i>p</i> -Cresol ¹	29.8	- 2.4	34.0	+11.54
<i>o</i> -Cresol ¹	24.2	-16.5	35.5	+15.50
Catechol	31.42	+ 1.82	35.5	+14.40
Resorcinol	31.50	+ 1.95	36.2	+19.10

solvents previously investigated. The values of the activation parameters for the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid in *o*-cresol, *p*-cresol and *m*-cresol are collected in Table 3 for comparison.

Discussion

The decarboxylation of malonanilic acid is kinetically first order over the temperature range investigated. It has been reported earlier that the hydroxyl groups of phenols associates with the carbonyl group of carboxylic acids⁹. In catechol two hydroxyl groups might be associating with malonanilic acid forming a bulkier complex than that of resorcinol, hence the decomposition rate is slow (Table 1).

The thermodynamic parameters were calculated using Eyring equation based upon the data of Table 1 and are shown in Table 2. Since the thermodynamic parameters of Table 2 for the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid is of the same order in both the solvents, it appears that the reaction mechanism in these solvents is identical. The data of Table 3 show that the values of enthalpy of activation and entropy of activation increase for the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid from *m*-cresol to resorcinol. Clark's results (Table 3, line 3) show that the stability of intermediate complex increased from *m*-cresol to *o*-cresol for the decarboxylation of malonic acid, whereas the stability of the complex decreased for malonanilic acid. The values of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the decarboxylation of malonic acid and malonanilic acid in the solvents of our investigations are approximately the same. The entropy of activation is more positive in resorcinol than any other solvent of Table 3 which indicates that the association is weaker in resorcinol. The high value of enthalpy of activation also indicates that a weaker attraction exists between malonanilic acid and resorcinol. The isolated group of resorcinol may cause an increase in the rate of reaction. Since the nature of the reaction in both the solvents is the same and similar to malonic acid, it can be predicted that the association is of molecular type. The structures of the complexes may be written in the following form.

A plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$ for the decarboxylation of malonanilic acid in cresol series in Table 3 is linear. The isokinetic temperature was calculated which corresponds to the melting point of malonanilic acid.

HAKEEM & HALEEM: THE KINETICS OF THE DECARBOXYLATION OF MALONANILIC ACID ETC.

This research supports the conclusion arrived at by Clark¹.

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References

1. L. W. CLARK, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1964, **68**, 2150.
2. M. A. HALEEM and M. AZEEM, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* 1973, **16**, 1.
3. M. A. HALEEM, M. NABI and M. A. HAKEEM, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.* 1970, **35**, 1607.
4. M. A. HALEEM and M. A. HAKEEM, *Austral. J. Chem.* 1976, (in press).
5. M. A. HALEEM, M. A. HAKEEM and J. SALAMAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1974, **51**, 645.
6. M. A. HALEEM, *J.U.A.R. Chem.* 1970, **13**, 505.
7. M. A. HALEEM and M. A. HAKEEM, J. SALAMAH and S. AHMED, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (In press).
8. M. A. HALEEM, *Bull. Coll. Sci. Univ. Baghdad*, 1969, **11**, 73.
9. M. A. HALEEM, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.* 1970, **35**, 2854.